

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

DISEASE RESISTANCE

Reaction to rice tungro-associated viruses of rice varieties with different genes for green leafhopper (GLH) resistance

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Rice varieties with different genes for resistance to GLH *Nephotettix virescens* were tested in the greenhouse for reactions to the rice tungro bacilliform (RTBV) and spherical (RTSV) viruses. Six-day-old seedlings of the test varieties were individually exposed for 1 d in test tubes containing 5 GLH that had fed on source plants infected with both viruses. Inoculated seedlings were indexed by the latex agglutination test 1 mo after inoculation.

Varieties with the same resistance genes reacted differently to infections with the viruses (see table). Jingasail and Pankhari 203 both have the same gene,

Reaction of CLH-resistant cultivars to rice tungro-associated viruses. IRRI, 1987.

Variety	Resistance gene ^a	Reaction to tungro ^b	Plants (no.) tested	Plant ^c (%)			
				RTBV+RTSV	RTBV	RTSV	Healthy
Pankhari 203	<i>Glh 1</i>	R	65	0	28	0	72
Jingasail	<i>Glh 1</i>	I	67	42	18	6	34
Palasithari 601	<i>Glh 2</i>	S	34	0	24	0	76
IR8	<i>Glh 3</i>	S	72	8	31	14	47
Ptb 18	<i>glh 4</i>	— ^d	54	13	37	0	50
IR42	<i>glh 4</i>	S	51	43	20	14	23
ASD8	<i>Glh 5</i>	I	42	2	26	0	72
TAPL 796	<i>Glh 6</i>	R	60	0	50	7	43
IR36	<i>Glh 6</i>	S	49	47	24	0	29
Modai Karuppan	<i>Glh 7</i>	I	71	47	11	4	38
TN1 (susceptible check)	None	S	63	87	8	5	0

^a Source: Karim and Pathak (1982), Siwi and Khush (1977). ^b Greenhouse mass screening data, IRRI Plant Pathology Department: 0-30% infection = resistant (R), 31-60% = intermediate (I), 61-100% = susceptible (S). ^c By latex test 30 d after inoculation. ^d Not tested.

Glh 1; but Jingasail was generally infected with both RTBV and RTSV, while Pankhari 203 was infected with RTBV alone. TAPL 796 and IR36 both have the *Glh 6* gene, but IR36 was generally infected with both viruses, while TAPL 796 was infected with only

RTBV. Ptb 18 and IR42 both have *glh 4*, but they reacted differently to either RTBV or RTSV. The results suggest that predominant infection with RTBV in GLH-resistant varieties is not associated with the major genes. □

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INSECT RESISTANCE

Effect of N nutrition and rice variety on leaffolder (LF), yellow stem borer (YSB), and grain yield

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We tested the response to N level of TM8089, a shortduration prerelease variety, at Tirur during 1985-86 navarai (Dec-Jan to Apr-May). The field trial in a strip-plot design had 3 varieties and 6 N levels; 0, 80, 100, 120, 140, and 160 kg/ha. The recommended varieties for the season — ADT36 and Vaigai (Co 37) — were used as checks.

Twenty-five-day-old seedlings were

planted in 20-m² plots at 15- × 10-cm spacing. Plots were fertilized with P and K at 50 kg/ha plus half the N basally before the last plowing. The remaining N was topdressed in 2 split doses at 15 and 30 d after transplanting (DT). The crop was sprayed with 250 ml phosphamidon/ha at 20 DT and with 500 ml monocrotophos/ha at 40 DT.

Rice LF and YSB appeared despite the insecticide treatment. LF damage was assessed at 50 DT on 20 plants/plot. The whiteheads caused by YSB in a 10-m² plot were counted at dough stage. Data on LF and YSB damage, and grain yield at harvest were statistically analyzed (see table).

N level and variety significantly

affected the pests and grain yield. Every increase in N caused an increase in LF and YSB infestation as well as in yield. The LF infestation level was below the economic threshold (10% leaf damage) up to 80 kg N/ha; maximum infestation was recorded at 160 kg N/ha. The yield increase was sharp and significant from 0 to 120 kg N/ha. From 120 kg N/ha, the yield differences between treatments were statistically nonsignificant.

At lower N levels, TM8089 was moderately susceptible to LF, and Vaigai and ADT36 were moderately resistant. But at higher N levels (140 and 160 kg/ha), TM8089 was highly susceptible.

Vaigai and TM8089 were moderately

